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Development and Characterisation of a Nano-composite Membrane Using Polyethersulphone and Graphene Oxide-Magnetite Nanoparticles for Rejection of Chromium Hexavalent Ions from Tannery Wastewater

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Abstract

Polyethersulphone (PES) polymer blended with Graphene Oxide (GO) and magnetite (nano-composite was synthesized using an immersion precipitation process for the filtration of chromium hexavalent ions from leather processing waste water. PES is a synthetic polymer with good chemical resistance, wide pH range (2-13) as well as good mechanical and thermal properties. However, it is hydrophobic and prone to fouling hence its limitations in aqueous separation processes. In order to improve hydrophilicity, porosity, permeability and strength properties of the polymeric membrane, GO was synthesized from coal via a modified Hummers Method and then blended with anhydrous ferrous chloride to form Graphene oxide/ magnetite () hybrid nano-particles. To assess the performance of the membrane pure water flux, Equilibrium Water Content (EWC) and tensile strength test was measured. Structural analysis involved porosity measurement. The filtration efficiency of the membranes was found by testing the waste water for chromium ion concentration before and after filtration. It was established that both the physical properties and chromium ion rejection improved with increase in polymer concentration and addition of hybrid nano-particles.

Keywords: Polyethersulphone, Graphene-magnetite nanoparticles, Nano-composite membrane

Introduction

Increasing demand for and shortage of clean water as a result of rapid urbanization, population growth, misuse, and climate disruption have become unprecedented urgent global issues. The increased concern about global environment pollution problems has resulted in the continuous expansion in finding new approaches to dealing

with heavy metal ions (1–5). Different from the organic components, heavy metallic ions are toxic, not degradable and have an infinite lifetime, thus they may be accumulated in living tissues, causing various diseases and environmental problems. Among these various kinds of metals, chromium is considered to be one of the most toxic (2–7).

Chromium is a heavy metal, naturally found in rocks and

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minerals, animals, and plants, with multiple applications in industry(3,4). Of interest to the present study is its use in the Leather Industry, where it is employed extensively as a tanning agent. However, only a fraction of the chromium salts used in the tanning process react with the skins and the rest of the salts remain in the tanning exhaust bath. Waste chrome from leather manufacturing, therefore, poses a significant disposal problem the discharging of a mass of Cr (VI) from industrial waste and sewage posing a serious threat on the health of the people and also on the surrounding industry(8).

Technologies normally employed for chrome remediation have several drawbacks (3,4,7,9–13). The insufficiencies in the traditional wastewater treatment methods have therefore sparked much interest in novel methods of water treatment such as membrane technology. Membrane processes have many distinct advantages. However, there are a number of drawbacks associated with membranes (11,12,14). In recent years to overcome these drawbacks, nanoparticles have been used to modify polymeric membranes to enhance the permeability, rejection, decrease fouling problems and reduce the investment and operational costs.

The aim of this study was to synthesise and characterise a PES/GO- nano-composite membrane for rejection of chromium from waste-water obtained from tanneries. In this work, GO- hybrid nano-particles were applied to PES matrix as a hydrophilic agent. The performance of the synthesized membranes was evaluated by flux, equilibrium water content, membrane porosity and chromium rejection.

Materials and Methods

Materials

All chemicals used in this investigation were of analytical grade and used without further purification treatment. Bituminous coal, sulfuric acid (95–97%), sodium nitrate (99.5%), nitric acid (65%), Iron (III) chloride hexahydrate (99.99%), iron (III) chloride tetrahydrate (99.99%), graphene oxide powder, Polyethersulphone (MW = 58000), Dimethyl Formadide (DMF), a glass plate and distilled water, standard chromium solution- 10µg/ml, diphenyl carbazide solution-0.15%w/w and sulphuric acid- 5%.

Synthesis of Graphene Oxide Nano-particles

Graphene oxide was prepared from bituminous coal by the Hummers method with a little modification (15,16). The coal was pulverised to obtain a powder using a pulveriser. 2g of the pulverised bituminous coal powder was added into 250ml beaker. Then 1g and 46ml were added sequentially under stirring in 24 hours. The mixture was further stirred for 6 hours at 80. The temperature was reduced to room temperature then the solution was diluted with 1M The

solution was centrifuged at 8000RPM until sedimentation was obtained. The sedimentation was then washed in aqueous ammonia.

Synthesis of Graphene-Magnetite hybrid Nano-particles

Graphene oxide-magnetite nano-particles were synthesized according to work done by Shahnaz Koushkbaghi et al (6). 0.5 g of synthesized GO was poured into 200 mL of distilled water under stirring for 30 min. 3.5 g of was then added into the mixture under stirring for further 30 min. After 0.65 g of was added into the mixture under vacuum for further 30 min. The GO/ hybrid nano-composite was dried in an oven at 50°C for 12 h.

Synthesis of Nano-composite membrane

PES/GO- nano-composite membranes were fabricated via phase inversion method (6,7,11). PES was used as bulk material, DMF as solvent, GO- nanoparticles as the additive and hydrophilic modifier, and DI water as the non-solvent in coagulation bath. Four different compositions of polymer solution were prepared, one containing 18% PES and 82% solvent, another containing 15% PES and 85% solvent, one containing 17.5% PES, 0.5% GO- and 82% solvent and finally the last one containing 14.5% PES, 0.5% GO- and 85% solvent.

Table 1. Composition of synthesized membranes

Membrane ID	Membrane composition (weight %)		
	PES	GO	Solvent
M1	15	-	85
M2	14.5	0.5	85
M3	18	-	82
M4	17.5	0.5	82

Membrane Characterisation

Thickness of Membrane

To measure the thickness of the membrane samples, a micrometre screw-gauge was used.

Equilibrium Water Content and Membrane Porosity

A gravimetric method was used to determine the Equilibrium water content and subsequently the porosity. Initially the membrane samples were dried in an air-circulating oven at 50 for 24 hours. Then the samples were cut into small pieces (1cm x 1cm) and weighed. The pieces were then immersed in distilled water at 25 for 24 hours. Droplets of water were removed from the surface of the membrane and then weighed again. Equilibrium water content was calculated using:

$$EWC = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1} \quad (1)$$

The porosity of the membranes was calculated using:

$$\epsilon = \frac{\frac{W_1 - W_2}{\rho_w} + \frac{W_2}{\rho_m}}{\frac{W_1 - W_2}{\rho_w} + \frac{W_2}{\rho_m}} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Where

w_1, w_2 are the wet and dry weights of the membrane respectively.

ρ_w is the density of distilled water (0.988g/ml)

ρ_m is the density of the polymer at 25 (11)

Tensile Strength Test

The tensile strength of the specimen was determined using the principle of constant rate of elongation (CRE). The membrane tensile strength test was carried out according to ASTM D882-10 Test Method for Tensile Properties of Thin Plastic Sheeting using a Testometric Micro 500 model tensile testing machine (17).

Filtration Experiments

Pure Water Flux

The water flux was measured over a period of 24 hours by measuring distilled water as permeate and was calculated over the time period using the following equation.

$$\text{Flux (J)} = \frac{Q}{A\Delta t} \quad (3)$$

Where Q is the quantity of water permeate (l)

A is the effective membrane area (m^2)

Δt is the sampling time (hr) (8,11)

Chrome Rejection Experiment

Chrome tanning waste water was used in the experiment. Permeate was collected after 24 hours for chromium analysis and the average concentration is computed. The percentage rejection was calculated using the following equation:

$$\%R = \left(1 - \frac{C_p}{C_f}\right) \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

Where R is the rejection of chromium (%);

C_p is the concentration of chromium in permeation solution;

C_f is the concentration of chromium (VI) in feed solution ($\mu\text{g/L}$) respectively [11].

Spectrophotometric Determination of Cr (VI) concentration in Water with Diphenyl-carbazide

The concentration of Cr (VI) ions in the water was determined before and after filtration. This was done by the use of an UV/VIS Spectrometer using the diphenyl carbazide method.

Results and Discussion

Membrane Thickness

Table 2. Thickness of synthesized membranes

Membrane identification	Average thickness (μm)
M1	30
M2	30
M3	56
M4	56

Effect of polymer concentration on thickness

It was found that with a casting depth of $300\mu\text{m}$ the membrane thickness increased from 30 to $56\mu\text{m}$ with an increase in polymer concentration from 15% to 18%. This is because the obtained membrane thickness is always smaller than the cast film thickness and for the same cast depth of the doctor blade, it decreases as the polymer content in the solution becomes lower [24],[25].

Effect of graphene oxide/magnetite nanoparticles

At a casting depth of $300\mu\text{m}$, it was observed that with the addition of the graphene oxide-magnetite nanoparticles there was no change in the resultant thickness of the membrane in comparison to the pristine PES membranes.

Figure 1. Membrane thickness results

Equilibrium Water Content and Membrane Porosity

The equilibrium water content (EWC) is considered a main characterisation parameter that indicates the hydrophobicity and hydrophilicity of a membrane. Moreover it is related to the porosity of a membrane. The porosity ϵ , is the ratio of the volume of pores to the total volume of the porous membrane. In this study a gravimetric method was used to determine the equilibrium water content and porosity and the results were as follows:

Table 3. Equilibrium Water Content and Porosity results

Membrane id	Porosity (%)	Equilibrium water content (%)
M1	69	71
M2	84	79
M3	56	63
M4	78	70

As the total polymer concentration increased from 15 % to 18 %, the porosity of membrane decreased from 69% down to 56%. This is because at a low total polymer content, the casting solution has low viscosity, and molecules move more freely, which is beneficial to the double-diffusion between water and solvent resulting in the formation of large pores and in turn formation of membranes with high porosity as well as Equilibrium Water Content (25). As the total polymer concentration increased to 18 weight %, both the viscosity of the casting solution and the mass transfer resistance of the solvent exchange increased. This impeded the interactions between solvent and non-solvent (water) when the nascent membrane is immersed into the coagulation bath. The crystallization rate of PES would be reduced, hence resulting in the formation of smaller pores adjacent to the top surface of the membrane. This results in reduced porosity and Equilibrium Water Content in the membranes (25-26). In contrast, if a lower polymer concentration used a membrane with high porosity and hydraulic permeability could be produced which consequently improve the potential of productivity.

Effect of Graphene oxide-magnetite nanoparticles on Equilibrium water content and porosity

The porosity of membranes enhanced with graphene oxide-magnetite nanocomposite have an increased porosity and equilibrium water content. This is in agreement with literature which states that the presence of surface oxidised graphene in polymeric membrane material would render it hydrophilic, affect the rate and speed of solvent-nonsolvent exchange in polymer separation and subsequently the final structure of the membrane(6,18,19). This was attributed to the presence of hydrophilic functional groups in /GO nano-hybrid which accelerate the membrane formation by speeding up the exchange rate between solvent and non-solvent phase, thus promoting the pores formation (18).

Figure 2. Equilibrium Water Content and membrane porosity results

Tensile Strength

The synthesized membrane samples were tested using a Testometric tensile strength tester, the results of these tests are given in the following table 3:

Table 4. Tensile test results

	Tensile strength (mPa)	Elongation @break (mm)
M1	0.1079	14.42
M2	0.1756	7.290
M3	0.156	14.73
M4	0.213	4.587

Effect of polymer concentration on tensile strength and breaking elongation

The strength as well as the elongation at break of the membranes increased with an increase in polymer concentration. The enhancement of mechanical strength is due to the change of the membrane structure from large pore to small pore structure, which led to a narrower pore size distribution and thus an increase in strength, as the total polymer concentration increases. Increase in polymer concentration also causes a denser packing of molecular chains in the resultant membrane. The total frictional force increase reduces molecular chain slippage so a stronger membrane is observed (20–23), (24).

Effect of Graphene oxide/ magnetite nanoparticles on tensile strength and breaking elongation

The tensile strength of the membranes improved with the addition of graphene oxide-magnetite nanoparticles as compared to the pristine PES membranes. According to literature the use of inorganic nano-particles in polymeric matrices could enhance the mechanical strength of the resultant composite membrane. The increase in strength is due to the interactions between nano-particles and polymer chains, which increases the rigidity of the polymer substantially and thus the energy required to break down the polymer chains. Also it is reported that when used as

nano-fillers in polymer membranes, graphene oxide and metal oxide nano-particles such as magnetite are expected to enhance the mechanical strength of the membrane and this is demonstrated in the tensile test results(25). However, with the addition of these nanoparticles a decrease in breaking elongation of the membranes was observed. Similar results were reported in work carried out by Ravishankar(26).

membrane, makes the membrane hydrophilic. Oxygen atoms mainly exist on graphene oxide as hydroxyl, epoxy and carbonyl groups and these attract water and hence improve the water flux(25,27,28). Also in a review done on the effects of inorganic nano-additives on properties and performance of polymeric membranes in water treatment, the contribution of nano-particles into the surface roughness might result in an increase in flux due to an enlargement in the efficient filtration area(19).

Figure 3. Tensile Strength results: Effect of GO/magnetite nanoparticles on tensile strength

Membrane Performance Evaluation

The effect of graphene oxide- magnetite nano-particles on pure water flux and rejection of chromium hexavalent ions was evaluated on membranes M1 and M2 only. The filtration system was based on Gravity Driven Membrane (GDM) ultrafiltration and the dead-end filtration mode was employed.

Pure Water Flux

The pure water permeability, also known as the pure water flux is defined as the volume of water that passes through a membrane per unit time, per unit area and per unit of trans-membrane pressure.

Table 5. Pure water flux values

Membrane identity	Pure water flux value, L/h
M1	10.475
M2	10.886

Effect of graphene oxide-magnetite nanoparticles on pure water flux

The pure water flux of the membranes enhanced with graphene oxide was more than that of the neat membranes. This is in accordance with literature. This is attributed to the fact that graphene oxide, present in the composite

Chromium Rejection Performance Evaluation

Table 5. Chromium rejection results

Metal	Initial conc (µg/l)	M1		M2	
		Final conc (µg/l)	% Re-removal	Final conc (µg/l)	% Re-removal
Cr(VI)	0.56	0.087	84.5	0.031	94.6

The rejection of the chromium hexavalent ions by the membranes is by size exclusion and adsorption mechanism. The results indicate that the modified PES-GO/Fe₃O₄ membrane is superior in performance to the neat PES membrane in all aspects of ultrafiltration. Both the neat and modified membranes showed good rejection properties with neat PES having 84% rejection and the composite PES/GO- membrane showing higher rejection of the chromium hexavalent ions at 94%. This may be attributed to the incorporation of magnetite nano-particles. Incorporation of these nanoparticles into the membrane structure leads to high adsorption efficiency, high removal rate of contaminants and this can be attributed to their high surface area and unique super-paramagnetism [12], [23]. When these magnetic Nano-adsorbents are used as hybrid Nano-particles with graphene oxide, selectivity and adsorption capacity increases due to increase in the

available adsorption sites for chromium.

The results obtained show that the synthesized PES/GO- nano-composite membranes may be successfully employed in environmental remediation as they exhibit a much higher removal efficiency than other polymer/nano-particle composite membranes that have been synthesized. In work done by Nermen Maximous(29) on the removal of heavy metals from wastewater by adsorption and membrane processes, it was found that PES/0.05% and PES/0.05% had 83.35% and 88.56% removal of chromium from wastewater respectively. Also it was shown that use of polymers as supports for graphene oxide and magnetite improves their removal efficiency of chromium and other heavy metals from water as compared to when they are used alone. In research done by J Zhu (30) it was found that when employed in chromium remediation, pure graphene nanocomposites had a removal efficiency of 44.4% whereas MGNCs had a higher removal efficiency of 52.6%, both results being lower than those of the synthesized PES/GO- membrane which had 94% removal efficiency.

Conclusion

Nano-composite membranes with different polymer concentrations were successfully developed via a simple dry/wet phase-inversion technique. The findings of this study prove that the polymer concentration and addition of Graphene oxide- magnetite nanocomposite greatly influence the membrane performance and morphology. Increase in the polymer concentration produced a denser and thicker membrane with decreased porosity as well as Equilibrium water content but with excellent mechanical properties. It was found that the modified membranes (PES-GO/Fe₃O₄ membranes) had the highest hydrophilicity, permeation flux as well as rejection capability.

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